

ROLE OF EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG YOUTH

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Abstract. A healthy lifestyle, like science, has not become a fashionable one-day thing, but has firmly established itself in the general education system of our country. Although it is not taught as a separate subject and has not found its place in the database of compulsory school subjects, a healthy lifestyle somehow manifests itself in such courses as natural history, biology, ecology, and even local history. Standards of living and health are today considered as the most important conditions for humanitarian progress and its criteria. This approach makes us consider a healthy lifestyle as a complex dynamic system characterized by family, household, social, labor and communicative activities. The harmonization of the system depends on the harmony of its subjects.

Keywords: living standards, health, ecology, healthy lifestyle, valeology.

Аннотация. Здоровый образ жизни, как и наука, не стал модной однодневкой, а прочно утвердился в системе общего образования нашей страны. На сегодняшний день преподается как отдельный предмет и нашел своего места в базе обязательных школьных предметов, здоровый образ жизни так проявляется в таких курсах, как природоведение, биология, экология и даже краеведение. Уровень жизни и здоровья сегодня рассматриваются как важнейшие условия гуманитарного прогресса и его критерии. Такой подход заставляет рассматривать здоровый образ жизни как сложную динамическую систему, характеризующуюся семейной, бытовой, социальной, трудовой и коммуникативной деятельностью. Гармонизация системы зависит от гармонии ее субъектов.

Ключевые слова: уровень жизни, здоровье, экология, здоровый образ жизни, валеология.

Relevance

A healthy lifestyle is seen as harmony with a harmonized person. A healthy lifestyle cannot exist without a person knowing about himself, about the regular changes that occur in the physical and mental state of a person, about the impact of these changes on the health of the individual, his intellectual development. A healthy lifestyle is at the heart of the subject of valeology. One has to hear the opinion that a healthy lifestyle is the name of what was previously done by doctors under the name "health education", "hygienic education", "hygienic education" or "healthy lifestyle". But this is the opinion of amateurs or those who have not made it difficult to look at the problem a little deeper than superficial similarities. A healthy lifestyle considers health problems, but not like medicine, but in contrast to it. The main subject of medicine is not health, but disease. For when a person is not sick, he does not go to the doctor. And treating the disease is more difficult than preventing it. A healthy lifestyle was conceived as a science dealing with human health. Whether within the framework of medicine or outside of it, the future will show, but the fact that it is necessary to study health, ways to preserve and strengthen it every day and preferably from a very early age. The subject of a healthy lifestyle is so great and significant that many specialists should deal with it - hygienists, physiologists, biologists, psychologists, environmentalists and, of course, teachers together with their parents. Two

branches have already separated from the trunk of general valeology. One is medical valueology, which deals with the development of health systems and methods, evaluation of their effectiveness, issues of preventing aging, activating reserve and adaptive capabilities, and the second branch is pedagogical valueology. Being in close connection with medicine and being created by physicians, valeology has now taken on the outlines of a pedagogical discipline. A healthy lifestyle is health through education. With this understanding, everything falls into place: it is necessary to deal with health not only and not so much where people come with their illnesses, but where they study (in kindergarten, school, college, institute), because health care must be taught. And the role of the teacher is assigned to parents, educators and teachers. The valueological approach to learning is to find ways to improve students' health before they get sick. And this is not limited to preventive measures. Here the task is deeper - to identify trends that would support and develop a person's desire to be healthy, to realize himself in the best possible way. The task of the teacher is to instill in a child or an adult the need to be healthy, to teach him this, to help in an organized manner in activities to preserve and strengthen health, and increase resilience. Teaching a person methods of restoring his health, strengthening the adaptive capabilities of the body is not just a humanistic task. It also has a high practical value, since it can be used by a person directly at school, to improve the assimilation of the school course. So, the content of the subject of valeology should be predominantly positive, that is, in the information and educational work of a valeologist teacher, the emphasis should be on explaining how to achieve mental and physical health, increase the body's resilience to external factors. The structure of the subject of pedagogical valueology. Pedagogical valueology includes the following components.

I. Theory and practice of a healthy lifestyle: what to do and, to a lesser extent, what not to do in order to achieve better health and maintain it, making the most of biological and psychological possibilities. The strategy for implementing this section is not to force a person to be healthy, not to scare him with the terrible consequences of bad habits, but to form a desire to be healthy, to cultivate the need for everyday purposeful activity in this direction. If a child is busy every day in training in the sports section, in classes at a music school and an art school, then he will not have time to sit in a noisy smoking or drinking company.

II. Psychological and pedagogical aspects of valeology. Here the main task is to help the child be at peace with himself and with other people - this is a guarantee and, at the same time, evidence of mental and mental health. Now the formula is valid: A healthy mind - a healthy body. In this direction, the closest contact and interaction between the teacher-valeologist and the psychologist is necessary.

III. Techniques and methods of self-regulation of processes and states. The inability to control the body likens a person to a pilot who knows little how to fly an airplane. Learn to control your body like an airplane in which you are going to fly: - this is the slogan for this section of valueology. It is fundamentally possible to achieve the desired results in a state of health, to provide the necessary and useful psychophysiological reactions in the following ways:

1. Medication-elementary method: with the help of pharmacological preparations and everything that we eat or drink. We know what a variety of effects can have on a person what he eats and drinks. The very act of eating has a calming effect on many. This method is a common cause of overweight and organ dysfunction.

2. Psychoregulatory method. Possession of methods of mental self-regulation should rightfully be considered as an integral component of a person's general culture.

3. Behavioral self-regulation. Physical activity, as a remedy for the blues, water procedures remarkably affect the mood and general condition of a person. Distraction helps to get rid of a bad mood, forget about pain, spend time with good and interesting people working on a common problem - improving health. IV. A mandatory section of pedagogical valueology is the impact of education on health. A lot has already been written about the deteriorating state of health of schoolchildren from class to class. Therefore, there is a need to conduct clear statistics on the dependence of the conduct of pedagogical valueology in the classroom and outside the school and changes in the child's health. Education should promote health, not deprive it. The entire teaching staff is responsible for the health and life of students in the school. How to save children from information overload, from the inevitable and rapidly emerging in the atmosphere of the regime and the difficult psychological climate of many schools, neuroses and psychosomatic diseases - these are just a small part of the problems that valueology teachers should know the answer to. The health of the younger generation is not only a social problem, but also a moral one. For a long time, the state of human health was associated with the interaction of two factors - heredity and the environment. This issue is considered at different levels, from local to global.

Conclusion. The main task of valeology at school is to motivate students for a healthy lifestyle, and it is natural that this can only be done taking into account the principles and methods of pedagogy. On the other hand, taking into account valeological approaches allows you to correctly build the pedagogical process itself and create the necessary external environmental conditions at school and at home. It is known that the system of education acts as a mechanism and method of reproduction of society. The goal of valeological education is the formation of a healthy person who is able to live happily ever after in society. The goal of valeological education is the formation of a healthy person who is able to live happily ever after in society. Achieving this goal is possible when solving both strategic and tactical tasks. The strategic task of valeological education can be represented, on the one hand, as obtaining the desired inclinations from the child, on the other hand, as the full development of these inclinations. The tactical task of valeological education lies in the formation of a schoolchild's attitude to a healthy lifestyle. Achieving this goal is possible when solving both strategic and tactical tasks. The strategic task of valeological education can be represented, on the one hand, as obtaining the desired inclinations from the child, on the other hand, as the full development of these inclinations. The tactical task of valeological education lies in the formation of a schoolchild's attitude to a healthy lifestyle. The teacher faces very important tasks: - to form in students a conscious and responsible attitude to the issues of protecting their own health; - to help the child realize that the main value of life is human health, for which he himself is responsible and himself is obliged to maintain it in a natural state; - to form preventive thinking on a healthy lifestyle; - to give children knowledge on the basics of personal hygiene, food culture, movement, sports; - include children in practical activities related to the development of the emotional sphere with the study of the fundamentals of the laws of ecology.

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